

EDUCATION OF PHYSICAL QUALITIES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract: This article examines ways in which physical education can improve children's health and physical development, increase their physical activity, develop physical skills, and shape healthy and harmonious individuals, with the aim of improving the preschool education system.

Keywords: physical, mental, and spiritual development, physical, social-emotional, speech and literacy training, hygienic conditions.

INTRODUCTION

Today, improving the preschool education system, strengthening the health of children and ensuring their physical development are one of the priority areas of state policy. The preschool period is an important stage in the physical, mental and spiritual development of a child, and it is during this period that healthy lifestyle skills are formed.

Physical education of preschool children serves to increase their motor activity, develop their physical qualities, and form a healthy and harmonious personality. Therefore, the study of the content and tasks of physical education on a scientific basis is of urgent importance.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Efim Aronovich Arkin (1873-1943) is a doctor of pedagogical sciences, a doctor and a pedagogical scientist. He created outstanding works in the field of children's physical education and children's hygiene. His works: "Preschool Age" (1948), "Guide to Parents and Education". He is a scientist who developed the laws of physical and mental development of different age groups.

The process of biological development of a child is studied by a complex of

natural sciences, the basis of which is the doctrine of I.M. Sechenov, I.P. Pavlov and their followers about the unity of the organism and the environment, the integrity of the organism and the regulatory role of the central nervous system in its vital activity.

The famous Greek philosopher Plato, speaking about happiness, said: “The first happiness for a person is his health, the second is beauty.” Indeed, health is the source of all wealth. The descendants of a people with a healthy and spiritual lineage will also be healthy, strong, faithful and loyal, and this happiness will become a powerful factor in the glory and power of the Motherland. A healthy generation is necessary for such happiness of the people.

The great jurist Abu Ali ibn Sino said, “Physical education is a great way to maintain health,” which is reminiscent of the proverb “Whoever does an action is a blessing in health.”

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The educational program in the preschool education system was created on the basis of state requirements for the development of preschool children, research conducted during the years of independence in the field of preschool didactics. The program covers the comprehensive preparation of children from the first year to 6-7 years old - physically, socially and emotionally, for speech reading and literacy, the main pedagogical tasks of children's cognitive processes, the necessary standards of knowledge, qualifications and skills that must be acquired. The task of the program is to develop the child physically, mentally and socially and emotionally and protect his health; to develop free thinking, creative abilities, create the necessary conditions for raising him as a morally and spiritually perfect person, as well as a complete person who will live independently and consciously in the future.

The following areas of development and preparation for school are considered the methodological basis:

- physical development of children, self-care and hygiene;
- socio-emotional development of children;
- readiness of children for speech, reading and literacy;
- educational tasks such as children's cognitive process, perception of the world around them and their understanding are included;
- the program has a focus on physical development of children, self-care and hygiene;
- the characteristics of children's development by age (from birth to 7 years); each age period is described, the main conditions for the physical development of

children are described.

The process of physical development is divided into the following stages:

1. Development of gross motor skills
2. Development of fine motor skills
3. Development of sensorimotor skills

The Concept of Preschool Education - indicators of a child's readiness for school education:

- Physical readiness (physiological level of child development);
- Psychological readiness (level of emotional, mental (intellectual), volitional development of the child's personality);
- Social readiness (level of meaningful social development of the child).

Development is a physical, mental and social process in a person, which includes all innate and acquired quantitative and qualitative changes.

Physical development is associated with growth, weight gain, improvement of sensory organs, and the ability to correctly control movements.

In mental development, significant changes occur in the formation of psychological qualities and traits in a person's personality, emotional, volitional, and cognitive processes.

The social development of a child is manifested in his behavior and attitude to his surroundings when he begins to participate in social life.

The development of a person as a person is carried out comprehensively and holistically in the unity of his physical and spiritual forces. The culture of worldview, beliefs, spiritual qualities, feelings (duty, conscience, responsibility, love) is created in specific historical and social conditions and affects the formation of the personality.

Physical development is a biological process that expresses the formation of the human body, a change in its forms and functions. In a narrow sense, these are anthropometric and biometric indicators: height, body weight, chest circumference, lung capacity, stature, etc. Physical development occurs in accordance with the laws of biological life - the unity of the environment and the organism, the systematic transition of quantitative changes to qualitative changes. Indeed, by changing living conditions, including physical education methods, it is possible to significantly increase the level of functional capabilities of the organism, change the indicators of physical development.

Physical education of preschool children is aimed at preserving their lives,

strengthening their health, forming motor skills and providing full-fledged physical education, forming cultural and hygienic skills, instilling the habit of living an orderly life.

The successful implementation of any work carried out in the education of a child depends on the health of the child. Therefore, most pedagogical work is carried out taking into account the physical capabilities and health of the child.

The physical development of a child is of great importance in his growth as a harmoniously developed person in all respects.

A healthy, physically strong child also has high working capacity, easily adapts to conditions, and easily and quickly performs various tasks.

When solving the tasks of physical education of preschool children, their age characteristics are taken into account. Rapid growth and development are a characteristic feature of the preschool child's organism. However, the formation of systems and their functions is incomplete. Therefore, a preschool child is very fragile. In this regard, the following health-improving tasks are given priority:

- 1) protection of life, combating disease, increasing the body's resistance to the effects of the external environment;
- 2) correct and timely development of all systems of the body, expanding their functional capabilities, harmonious physical development of the correct height - physique.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Modern developing pedagogical technologies are aimed not only at the educational process, but also at the child's mental processes, his personal qualities, intellectual and creative abilities, and physical development. In the context of humanistic education, pedagogical technologies are seen in the context of a serious attitude of the teacher to the child.

When pedagogical technologies are used in pedagogical processes, their effectiveness is diagnosed. This ensures that the child has an open attitude to the impact of education.

There is some commonality in the physical and spiritual development of children, but the characteristics, abilities and inclinations, interests, and willpower of children are different. These differences are reflected in their behavior, study, and work. A method that is useful for one student may be ineffective when applied to another. Therefore, it is advisable to study the characteristics of each student.

The algorithm for managing the effectiveness of preschool education, that is,

the systematic rules of monitoring, is determined by observing and correcting the reception activities of children in fulfilling the set educational and educational goals.

Identifying problems in the physical development of children and determining measures to prevent them, constantly analyzing the physical development of children, cooperating with parents on the physical development of children, explaining the importance of a healthy lifestyle and implementing it in the educational process.

For the proper physical development of children, it is necessary to create hygienic conditions (buildings, playgrounds, equipment, clothing - headgear, footwear), to strictly follow a scientifically based regime of children's life (which includes rational nutrition, development of movements and measures to strengthen the body). At the same time, constant supervision by medical workers, necessary preventive and treatment work are required.

Rooms are allocated for each group in preschool educational organizations. Group rooms should be large enough to allow children to move freely and breathe fresh air, bright, dry and warm, with windows facing south-east.

The height of the group room is 3-3.5 m, and each child should have 2.5 sq. m of space above the building level, about 8 cubic meters of air; the room decoration should be hygienic, easy to clean, pleasant, soft colors. It is necessary to maintain order in the group. The room should not have heavy and thick curtains, carpets, soft furniture, or anything superfluous that blocks light. All equipment should be suitable for educational purposes, the height and body structure of children, and meet the special standards set by the Ministry of Public Education.

Children's tables and chairs should be quite durable and lightweight, simple in structure and easy to wash. Tables should be placed so that the light falls from the left side. Toys and visual aids should also meet hygienic requirements, be of a solid, harmless color, and have a smooth appearance.

The educator is responsible for the hygienic conditions of his group. The room should be ventilated after the children go for a walk or to music lessons, and the windows should always be open, regardless of the season.

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